

Role of cover crop roots in soil organic carbon accrual—A review

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Abstract

Appropriate cover crop (CC) management is an important tool for the improvement of soil carbon stock; however, the relationships between carbon accumulation and CC root traits remain unclear. A literature review was performed to identify the extent and focus of recent research and to answer questions about the role of root traits of CCs in soil C accumulation with regard to species selection, mixture composition and agronomic management. The findings based on the analysis of 69 publications show that a range of root traits such as root biomass, architecture, depth of rooting, root chemical composition, as well as quantity and quality of rhizodeposition, can contribute to soil structure formation and C accumulation. These traits are usually species specific, and it seems that appropriate species combinations in the mixtures can offer the highest potential for optimization of C stock across various environments. However, there has been twice as much recent research on roots of CC monocultures than on mixtures, with little attention paid to agronomic aspects such as plant spatial arrangement or soil tillage in relation to CC root development. Considerations of real management under field conditions could be beneficial in providing greater accuracy of estimation of the contribution of CCs in increasing the SOC stock in croplands.

KEYWORDS

agronomy, catch crops, EJPSOIL, root architecture, soil organic matter

1 | INTRODUCTION

Adoption of cover crops (CCs) management into agronomic practice is considered to be an option to help increase soil organic carbon (SOC) stock. This can occur by direct C allocation from the crop to the soil and also by improving the C input from the following cash crops, as shown in the organic cropping

system (Amsili & Kaye, 2021). Several studies have shown that CCs are effective in SOC accrual, if their use replaces a fallow period, across various environments (Bergtold et al., 2019; Cordeiro et al., 2022; Duval et al., 2016; Qin et al., 2023) or if they support perennial crops (Nieto et al., 2013). However, CCs may not increase SOC stock in all cases (Ladoni et al., 2016), and Chaplot and Smith (2023) suggested that the overall positive effect

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of CCs on SOC stock may have been significantly overestimated. In a study across the United States, it was found that CCs did not provide a significant amount of SOC stock in two-thirds of comparisons (Blanco-Canqui, 2022). Lower CC efficiency in SOC stock could be explained by the priming effect or by issues associated with spatial heterogeneity of SOC content at sampling times (Poeplau & Don, 2015) as well as by the requirement of available nutrients for soil organic matter formation (Chaplot & Smith, 2023). The efficiency should be examined under combined effects with other management practices and environments (Bai et al., 2019) and these studies should follow proper terminology (Don et al., 2024) as well as adequate CC experiment methodology (Chaplot & Smith, 2023). According to Seitz et al. (2023), CCs alone cannot turn croplands from carbon sources to carbon sinks as they cannot prevent soils from losing SOC storage without further transforming agricultural production. However, the benefits of CC cannot be limited just to that of increasing SOC storage as they may also have valuable environmental benefits to support sustainable agricultural systems (Abdalla et al., 2019; Gollner et al., 2020; Sias et al., 2021).

In recent reviews or meta-analyses, considerable effort has been devoted to demonstrating the positive general effect of CCs on soil properties, especially SOC stock (Fageria et al., 2005; Jian et al., 2020; Koudahe et al., 2022; Poeplau & Don, 2015) and the necessity of proper methodology for conducting meta-analyses was highlighted by Fohrafellner et al. (2023). The growth of CCs can bring an average SOC accrual rate of 0.33 MgC ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (Qin et al., 2023) or a 6% increase of SOC content (Bai et al., 2019) indicating there is a clear positive effect of CCs on SOC stock (Poeplau et al., 2024). The role of CC roots has been reviewed with a focus on root–soil interaction in association with methods for root evaluation (Ogilvie et al., 2021) and with regard to a provisioning role in delivering below-ground ecosystem services (Griffiths et al., 2022). Indeed, the CC roots play a pivotal role in SOC storage (Kemper et al., 2020) in situations where the CCs allocated nearly equal proportions of C and N to above-ground and below-ground fractions (de Notaris et al., 2020). Some studies have reported that CC roots were found to contribute equally, or more, to the relatively stable C pool than above-ground C-input despite a smaller mass (Austin et al., 2017; Ladoni et al., 2016). Whilst it is well known that root systems play a major role in SOC supply and storage, exactly which root characteristics are important for maximizing SOC gains and for ensuring long-term SOC storage is not obvious (Jansson et al., 2021). Similarly, the relationships between CC root traits and soil properties, such as SOC storage, soil organic matter and soil aggregate-size classes, are still largely unclear (Saleem et al., 2020) and

Highlights

- Cover crop mixtures can provide a clear benefit from an appropriate combination of root traits supporting soil structure together with soil C stock.
- The majority of field cover-crop research (two-thirds) dealing with root traits has been conducted with monocultures.
- Cover crop root development is different in ‘semi-artificial’ field experiments and practical field conditions that can be significantly modified by a range of constraints.
- Under cover crop growth limitation, spontaneous flora can also have some potential benefits without additional costs.

factors affecting root trait development and the processes through which they contribute to soil C input have received less attention.

Crop performance is generally related to its root development over time (Hakl et al., 2017), and the benefits attributed to incorporating CCs into agroecosystems are realized only under adequate CC root and shoot productivity (Brant et al., 2011). According to Qin et al. (2023), the SOC benefits from CCs can be maximized by optimizing CC management practices such as selecting particular types of CC or by controlling CC growth. However, there is only limited research available on the agronomic aspects of CCs and there is a need here to determine how to maximize the benefits of specific CCs for particular environments, rather than to focus simply on the general effects of CCs as a whole group. Here, the relationship between CC management and the development of root traits requires special attention, although field-scale investigations of roots are highly time-consuming and complex (Amsili & Kaye, 2021) and generalizations are limited in part by the variable methods in use.

There remains a considerable knowledge gap in the agronomic aspects of CCs in relation to their root performance through which they contribute to associated ecosystem services. Therefore, we have reviewed the literature on CC root development and associated root traits in relation to agronomic aspects and SOC supply with respect to the environment. The review provides an overview of published papers covering CC roots and SOC storage with regard to regions, climatic zones, or types of studies with a special focus on the agronomic aspects of farmer decision making, such as CC species selection, their mixture composition or sowing dates. The topic of this review is summarized into these three aims:

FIGURE 1 Overview of reviewed 93 studies following the search string ('cover crop*') AND ('root*') AND ('SOC' OR 'soil organic carbon') in the topic (black bar). Number of studies from the search string concerning separate keywords or their combinations were divided into two groups: 'Cover crops or SOC or root data measured or analysed' (grey bars) and 'Cover crops or SOC or root data only discussed' (dotted bars).

(i) identify which root traits influence the CC below-ground biomass contributions to SOC stock or its fraction; (ii) investigate which species or mixtures promote desirable root traits associated with root carbon inputs; and (iii) evaluate which CC type of CC management is most beneficial for root development and carbon inputs. The results are presented of an evaluation of 69 peer-review journal articles in Web of Science using a combination of keywords 'cover crop' and 'root' and 'soil organic carbon' in the topic. These articles following a search query: TS = ('cover crop*' AND root* AND (soc OR 'soil organic carbon')) and were published between 1990 and 2022.

2 | CURRENT CC RESEARCH INVOLVING SOC STORAGE AND CROP ROOTS

The keyword 'cover crop*' appears in the topics of more than 10,000 studies, whilst in association with 'SOC', it drops to about 1000 papers. The combination of the keywords 'cover crop*' and 'SOC' is associated with roots in 93 articles, representing only 10% of these publications. After surveying the selected articles, it was found that 78% were dealing with CCs, whilst 22% only used the keyword in the topic in some broader context. These articles have been excluded from subsequent analyses. A list of all 93 articles is shown in Appendix 1, where selected articles dealing directly with CCs (69) are marked. Amongst these 69 articles, 51 articles can be classified as case studies including CC experiment (Figure 1, marked in Appendix 1), 15 as reviews and 3 meta-analyses. Figure 1 shows that about 90% of the reviewed studies mentioned CC together with 'SOC'. The CC roots and 'SOC' have been analysed or discussed in more than

60 articles, but whilst SOC storage is directly analysed in approximately 75% of these studies, roots are measured only in 35%. There are only 16 articles combining CC roots and SOC measurements, demonstrating that soil SOC storage in combination with CC roots is much more often just discussed than directly measured.

After excluding those publications in which the term CCs was only referred to but without data or discussion of the topic, the remaining 69 articles were categorized into groups in line with the aim of the study, which is presented in Figure 2. Figure 2a shows the distribution of these publications over time and indicates a strong increase in the number of articles on the topic in the past 5 years. Figure 2b indicates that around three-quarters of the research represents articles based on a field environment, and only one-quarter of investigations were focused on CC effects in long-term cultures (vineyards, orchards or olive groves). The use of greenhouse/growth chamber studies is negligible here. Although the studies cover different climatic zones relatively uniformly (Figure 2c), most were from Europe and North America, suggesting there has been less research effort on this topic in Asia, Australia and South America, and no articles from Africa (Figure 2d).

3 | CC ROOT TRAITS ASSOCIATED WITH SOC STOCK IMPROVEMENT

Root measurements can help with the estimation of CC carbon inputs (Amsili & Kaye, 2021) where the contribution to SOC stock from root carbon inputs is equal to, or greater than, that from above-ground biomass (Austin et al., 2017). As is illustrated in Figure 1, only 20% of reviewed articles on CCs and SOC stock include information on root measurement, probably due to the labour-intensive requirements of

FIGURE 2 Overview of reviewed 69 studies dealing with cover crops in relation to (a) date of publishing, (b) agricultural systems where CCs were introduced, (c) climatic zone and (d) region. (NA. = not applicable).

root measurements compared to that of above-ground biomass. In this section of the paper, the following five subsections deal with individual groups of root traits and their effects on soil properties, with a focus on the formation of soil structure and improving SOC storage. The available effects of particular CC root traits on soil properties are summarized in Table 1, together with their potential to increase the SOC stock. The mutual relations between the roots of CCs and the SOC stock are shown in Figure 3. concerning important groups of root traits defined in this section.

3.1 | Total root biomass

Total root weight per area or volume unit remains the most frequently assessed root trait, which was analysed

in about 40% of the reviewed CC case studies and has a clear relationship to direct C allocation into the soil (Rossi et al., 2020) and larger CC root biomass increases SOC benefits (Qin et al., 2023). Positive correlation with SOC stock has been also observed for CC above-ground biomass (Blanco-Canqui, 2022) since combined above- and below-ground biomass add additional C to the system (Qin et al., 2023). The proportion of root C allocation, rhizodeposition and the amount released as CO₂ is considered to be equal for a range of species (Pausch & Kuzyakov, 2017). Therefore, in models, total root biomass could be a basic predictor for an estimation of rhizodeposition (e.g., Seitz et al., 2023) when the greater root mass simply results in greater rhizodeposition, which leads to a greater soil C supply. Although authors have generally advocated that CC should have a high root mass (Kemper et al., 2020), Jansson et al. (2021) suggested that breeding

TABLE 1 Effects of root traits grouped as root biomass amount or distribution, root architecture and root chemical composition on soil properties and their influence on SOC stock improvement.

Root traits	Soil effect	SOC stock	References
Total root biomass	Greater root biomass improves soil C input	+	Jansson et al. (2021)
	Greater root biomass is not necessarily translated into SOC gains due to enhanced microbial activity and priming	?	
	Higher root biomass increases C in the coarse silt fraction	+	Rossi et al. (2020)
Root mass density	Supports SOC content	++	Ali et al. (2023)
	Supports soil aggregate stability	+	Garcia et al. (2019)
Root volume density	Poor relationships to SOC enhancement	?	Ali et al. (2022)
Root elongation rate	Related to higher exudates production and C accumulation into the C _{SILT} pool	+	Rossi et al. (2020)
Root:shoot ratio	Larger root:shoot ratio increases SOC benefits from CCs	+	Oin et al. (2023)
Depth of rooting	Deep rooting explores the soil volume more completely, improving soil structure	+	Kemper et al. (2020)
Root diameter	Greater diameter negatively correlated with C in the POM fraction	-	Rossi et al. (2020)
	Diameter increases C in the coarse silt fraction	+	
	Coarse roots increase soil macroporosity	?	Ogilvie et al. (2021)
	Poor relationships to SOC enhancement	?	Ali et al. (2022)
	Fine roots coalesce aggregates	+	Ogilvie et al. (2021)
	Grass fine roots have better penetration into deeper layers of clayey soil compared to tap-rooted rape or lucerne	+	Ali et al. (2022)
	Tap-rooted cover crops penetrate better than rye through compacted soil layers	+	Chen and Weil (2010)
	Fine roots contribute to rhizodeposition, maximal exudation rates	+	Kravchenko et al. (2019)
Root length	Fine roots increase pore space and soil porosity	+	Hudek et al. (2022)
	Root length density (RLD) supports POM content	++	Rosolem et al., 2016
	RLD improves a soil structure, explores better the soil volume	+	Kemper et al. (2020)
	RLD increases macroaggregate proportion, aggregate stability and water infiltration	++	Ali et al. (2022)
	Specific root length showed a negative correlation with aggregate stability	?	Garcia et al. (2019)
C:N	Negative relationship between RLD and C:N ratio	?	Wendling et al. (2016)
	Higher C:N support C accumulation in the unprotected coarse POM fraction	+	Rossi et al. (2020)
Hemicellulose, water-soluble compounds	Labile C is a source for microbes – necromass – MOAM	+	Rossi et al. (2020)
	Negatively correlated with C in the POM fraction	-	
Lignin/cellulose ratio	Lower ratio supports SOC accumulation	++	Ali et al. (2022, 2023)
Lignin and cellulose	Higher content of slow degradable compounds increases the POM pool	+	Rossi et al. (2020)
Root exudates	Root exudates contribute to the chemical heterogeneity of SOM	?	Kallenbach et al. (2016)

Note: ‘++’ positive effect published; ‘+’ positive effect can be expected; ‘?’ zero or variable effect; ‘-’ negative effect.

FIGURE 3 Diagram presenting factors affecting cover crops roots development and relationships between cover crops root traits and SOC formation (POM = particulate organic matter).

for higher root biomass may not necessarily be the answer to faster and more effective SOC storage. A trait with practical importance could be the higher root:shoot ratio as if more of the CC biomass is allocated to below-ground than above-ground, the SOC benefit could be greater (Qin et al., 2023). The ratio also can help with root biomass estimation (Fuksa et al., 2013), although it has been suggested that above-ground C may not be a good predictor of below-ground C, and that root C inputs to soil are independent of above-ground biomass yield (Mortensen et al., 2021). For Denmark, Hu et al. (2018) suggested that using fixed values for below-ground C pools based on farming system and species (as the most influential factors) may be more accurate than using fixed allometric relations, such as root:shoot ratios, where organic farming systems provide higher root biomass. Rossi et al. (2020) also found that the more rapid root elongation rate promoted C accumulation into the mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) pool.

3.2 | Root distribution in a soil profile

The depth of rooting also plays a significant role in the context of soil carbon stock and this trait has been promoted as a goal in plant breeding (Graham et al., 2023; Kell, 2011). The trait is investigated in CC studies (Griffiths et al., 2022) because C deposited at depth may have greater residence

time due to its slower decomposition rate in the deeper layers of soil profiles (Jansson et al., 2021), in association with lower microbial activity. Kemper et al. (2020) consider that deep rooting into the subsoil is an efficient trait for exploring the soil volume more completely and for increasing SOC storage. Although it is generally assumed that the roots of tap-rooted crops are able to penetrate compacted soil better than fibrous-rooted crops, the study of Ali et al. (2022) demonstrated better penetration of the fibrous roots of vetiver grass (*Chrysopogon zizanioides*) into deeper layers of clayey soil, in comparison with rape (*Brassica napus*) and tap-rooted lucerne (*Medicago sativa*). This was attributed to a higher proportion of fine roots and high root tensile strength which provided a high root-drilling ability into the compacted deep soils with a small proportion of soil capillary pores. Evaluating root formation in 3D, Burr-Hersey et al. (2017) reported that the root systems of both tillage radish (*Raphanus sativus*) and black oat (*Avena strigosa*) were better suited for encountering a compacted soil layer and in effecting soil structural amelioration, compared with vetch (*Vicia sativa*).

3.3 | Root architecture traits

Apart from root amount and depth, there are many other root parameters that could be measured by various

methods and provide some relationship to SOC content (Ali et al., 2022). Only 10% of the CC articles examined in this review deal with root architecture traits in relation to SOC storage, and it remains unclear how combinations of root traits affect multiple soil properties (Hudek et al., 2022) as the understanding of relationships between C accumulation and root morphological traits is challenging (Rossi et al., 2020). From the findings summarized in Table 1, it seems that the positive effect of root length on SOC storage has been consistently supported in a range of studies, and Kemper et al. (2020) concluded that high root length density (RLD) in topsoil is an efficient trait for improving soil structure and SOC storage in arable soils. Traits such as root diameter or root biomass density showed poor relationships to SOC content enhancement (Ali et al., 2022). Rossi et al. (2020) showed that specific plant root traits influence the accumulation of C into different SOC fractions, largely through the mediation of microbial activity in relation to the recalcitrance of root tissues. They also found that the greater root length production of old roots promoted C accumulation into the C_{SILT} pool (MOAM), but smaller root diameter and low content of easily degradable compounds enhanced C accumulation into the POM pool. In contrast to root length, the role of root diameter seems to be more variable in relation to the SOC storage, where the positive effect of fine roots on soil structure is relatively consistent but it may not have resulted in SOC increase.

3.4 | Root chemical composition and rhizodeposition

Apart from root morphology, the explanatory power of CC root traits in relation to soil properties is also closely associated with root chemical composition (Garcia et al., 2019). According to Rossi et al. (2020), root hemicellulose content was negatively correlated with C in the POM fraction, whereas root traits increasing chemical recalcitrance promote short-term C stabilization by slowing the root decomposition rate. The lower lignin/cellulose ratio was more favourable for higher SOC accumulation allowing hydrolysing enzymes to have easier access to the substrate with increased degradability (Ali et al., 2023).

Plant C input is substantially underestimated if plant C deposition through the roots was not considered (de Notaris et al., 2020). Rhizodeposition was assumed to be roughly 31% of the root biomass for the estimation of CC carbon input in a model (Seitz et al., 2023). Mortensen et al. (2021) point out the importance of ensuring precise calculation of phyllo- and rhizodeposition, as many published estimates are substantially overestimated when applied in a true field situation. The quality of rhizodeposition depends on root

traits associated with higher input of the C labile fraction which promotes microbial residue formation (Rossi et al., 2020) and microbial-derived compounds make up a large proportion of stable SOC stock (Kallenbach et al., 2016). However, there is a risk that the input of highly degradable C through plant deposition may increase the release and priming of C in the MAOM fraction (Rossi et al., 2020).

3.5 | Root traits and soil structure formation

Amongst the plant root traits of CCs that merit consideration are the characteristics of the root system morphology conducive to soil structure formation (Jansson et al., 2021) because there are significant interactions between CC root systems and soil physical properties (Ogilvie et al., 2021). The effect of CC roots on soil aggregation can be attributed directly to the root architecture traits, but root biomass or rhizodeposition also further influenced aggregates through their indirect modification of SOC content which plays the dominant role in increments of aggregation and mean weight diameter (Ali et al., 2022). These two effects are rather difficult to separate; however, in some cases, the role of SOC content seems more important than functional root traits (Garcia et al., 2019). For soil structure, total root length and root surface area correlate well with aggregate stability and soil macroporosity (Hudek et al., 2022). In vineyards with soils that had low SOC content, the CC root mean diameter and root mass density showed positive correlations with aggregate stability whilst specific root length showed a negative correlation (Garcia et al., 2019). According to Kravchenko et al. (2019), plant roots are the key agents in the formation of soil pore architecture and plant root systems that stimulate the creation of 30–150 µm pores enhance opportunities for microbial decomposition products to reach inaccessible soil matrix and thus stimulate C gains. The positive role of CC roots on SOC improvement through aggregate properties in clayey red soil was confirmed by Ali et al. (2022), where fibrous-rooted vetiver grass provided higher RLD and a greater percentage of fine and medium roots together with increased soil macroaggregate (>2 mm) proportion, aggregate stability and water infiltration in comparison with tap-rooted CC. Similarly, Hudek et al. (2022) observed a negative relationship between average root diameter and soil macroporosity indicating that CC with fine roots is more beneficial for creating pore-space than those with thicker taproots. However, despite the expected effects that CC roots have on soil structure, SOC content was unchanged during the 4-year period of observation, although a positive effect of rye CC on soil

FIGURE 4 Overview of reviewed 51 case studies including cover crops experiments concerning extension of various CC plant family, CC monocultures and different mixtures, growth period, soil tillage before sowing and weed management (dark bars).

aggregate mean weight diameter (MWD) has been observed (Rorick & Kladivko, 2017).

4 | ROOT FORMATION AND C INPUT IN RELATION TO SPECIES SELECTION AND MIXTURE COMPOSITION

Factors affecting CC root development are summarized in Figure 3. Selection of CC species (or their mixture composition) together with their methods of establishment, sowing date and seed sowing rate, could all be considered as components of a key farmer tool for the adaptation and successful management of CCs into the whole cropping system. Additionally, it must be considered that CCs are a highly heterogeneous group of crops that have differing requirements in terms of their sowing dates and management, and the way they are used.

The use of variable CC species, mixtures and sowing dates was analysed in 51 articles including CC experiments (Figure 1, Appendix 1) with the aim of presenting the extent of current research. This overview is presented in Figure 4 and is commented upon in particular sub-sections below. In Table 2, differences are summarized for root diameter, dry mass and length in the topsoil layer together with root depth amongst the most frequent CC plant families when cultivated as monocultures, based on studies comparing root traits amongst species.

4.1 | CC species selection and breeding

The key plant families investigated for CC cultivation are *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae* and *Brassicaceae*. These are shown in Figure 4, illustrating the number of articles for each plant family with cereals and perennial grasses distinguished within the *Poaceae*. These results are in line with the main functional groups described by Griffiths et al. (2022). Comparison of selected root traits amongst these CC plant families is summarized in Table 2, illustrating differences between families as well as high diversity within each family across species. There is a clear potential for species of *Brassicaceae* to improve root diameter especially, whilst *Poaceae* can exhibit improved root length density. Differences were less pronounced for other parameters.

The differences amongst CC species in root traits have been widely reported (Griffiths et al., 2022; Hudek et al., 2022). This could be manifested in differences in both above- and below-ground biomass production in relation to SOC storage improvement (Cordeiro et al., 2022) or in a negative relationship between root length density and C:N ratio (Wendling et al., 2016). Therefore, the selection of appropriate species offers the potential for significant impacts on root biomass production and associated CC functions. In line with the role of species or their combinations, advancement in phenotyping approaches allows the simultaneous selection of root and shoot traits and the devising of CC mixtures that enhance functional diversity in the field (Griffiths et al., 2022). Although promising root phenotyping and genetic approaches can be effective for the development of new varieties of CC perennial grasses

TABLE 2 Overview of root diameter (RD), root length density (RLD), root dry matter (RDM) and specific root length (SRL) in top-soil layer together with root length and depth within given families cultivated as cover crops.

Parameter	Fabaceae	Poaceae	Brassicaceae	Boraginaceae	References
RD (mm)	0.92 (MS)	0.95 (CZ)	1.11 (BN)	-	Ali et al. (2022)
	0.42 (VV)	0.36–0.41 (SC-ASa)	14.09–107.00 (SA-RS)	0.28 (PT)	Hudek et al. (2022)
	0.22–0.37 (PS-VF)	0.21–0.28 (SI-SS)	0.19–0.30 (SA-RS)	0.20 (PT)	Wendling et al. (2016)
RLD (cm.cm ⁻³)	3.50 (MS)	2.82 (CZ)	2.56 (BN)	-	Ali et al. (2022)
	0.31–1.52 (LA-TI)	1.03–2.47 (ASt-SC)	1.19–1.28 (RS-BR)	0.40 (PT)	Kemper et al. (2020)
	0.37 (VV)	4.45–5.08 (ASa-SC)	0.84–2.65 (RS-SA)	2.06 (PT)	Hudek et al. (2022)
	2.1–4.2 (VV-TI)	4.0–13.5 (HV-T)	2.5 (BJ)	-	Griffiths et al. (2022)
	2.40–3.64 (PS-TAl)	4.63–7.41 (SI-ASt)	3.52–6.16 (SA-BJ)	5.27 (PT)	Wendling et al. (2016)
RDM (mg.cm ⁻³)	4.75 (MS)	1.80 (CZ)	0.75 (BN)	-	Ali et al. (2023)
(g.m ⁻²)	60 (VV)	70–190 (ASa-LM)	140 (BN)	50 (PT)	Hu et al. (2018)
(g)	0.24–2.31 (PS-VF)	0.60–1.42 (SI-SS)	0.89–4.77 (BJ-RS)	0.71 (PT)	Wendling et al. (2016)
SRL (m.g ⁻¹)	62.5 (VV)	38.7–54.8 (ASa-SC)	2.5–6.5 (RS-SA)	79.9 (PT)	Hudek et al. (2022)
	18–138 (VF-PS)	44–114 (SS-ASt)	11–99 (RS-BJ)	105 (PT)	Wendling et al. (2016)
	75–110 (MS-VV)	120–165 (TAe-SC)	85 (BJ)	-	Griffiths et al. (2022)
Root length (m)	30.6–46.4 (PS-TAl)	59.1–94.5 (SI-ASt)	45.0–78.6 (SA-BJ)	67.3 (PT)	Wendling et al. (2016)
Root depth (cm)	31–63 (MS-VV)	53–77 (HV-T)	63 (BJ)	-	Griffiths et al. (2022)
	62–71 (TI-LA)	79–81 (SC-ASt)	88–89 (BR-RS)	77 (PT)	Kemper et al. (2020)

Note: Values represented means of single species or ranges if more species within each family were included in the case study. Acronyms of species representing mean or maximal/minimal values are in brackets.

Abbreviations: ASa, *Avena sativa* L.; ASt, *Avena strigosa* Schreb.; BJ, *Brassica juncea* (L.) Czern.; BN, *Brassica napus* L.; BR, *Brassica rapa* L. var. *silvestris* (Lam.) Briggs; CZ, *Chrysopogon zizanioides* L.; HV, *Hordeum vulgare* L.; LA, *Lupinus angustifolius* L.; LM, *Lolium multiflorum* Lam.; MS, *Medicago sativa* L.; PS, *Pisum sativum* L.; PT, *Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth; RS, *Raphanus sativus* L.; SA, *Sinapis alba* L.; SC, *Secale cereale* L.; SI, *Setaria italica* (L.) P. Beauv.; SS, *Sorghum sudanense* (Piper) Stapf; TAe, *Triticum aestivum* L.; TAl, *Trifolium alexandrinum* L.; T, *xTriticosecale* Wittmack; TI, *Trifolium incarnatum* L.; VF, *Vicia faba* L.; VV, *Vicia villosa* L.

(Graham et al., 2023), there are many constraints – including laboriousness, unsuitability of most methods for large series of samples, high variability of populations, together with the great influence of environmental variations. These limits together result in root traits not being included in the breeding objectives of CCs. The objectives are instead usually focused on direct agronomic traits of CCs, such as improving the proportion of soft seeds in hairy vetch (Riday et al., 2023).

4.2 | Benefits of CC root system in mixtures

Although a CC monoculture is easier to manage in the field (Brant et al., 2011) and is often used in different models (Seitz et al., 2023), there is a significantly greater potential for different CC mixtures to provide productivity improvement (Amsili & Kaye, 2021). Similarly, the enhanced yield effect in legume–grass mixtures occurs in forage production (Hakl et al., 2018), amongst others, in relation to N transfer from the legume component.

The yield benefit of mixtures is generally associated with species complementarity and competition; these are considered as major determinants of the productivity and functioning of plant communities (Saleem et al., 2020). In a tropical environment, even simple bi-cultures of some specific legume and non-legume CCs (triticale + white clover, sorghum + hemp and okra + cowpea) can improve biomass accumulation dramatically in comparison with their cultivation as single species (Wang et al., 2012). There can even be consequences for increased productivity in crop systems, and a legume + non-legume mixed CC improved the main crop yield significantly in contrast to the legume or non-legume CC (Abdalla et al., 2019). Qin et al. (2023) reported a negative impact of non-legume CC on following maize yield in comparison with legume CC, which could be explained by a larger C:N ratio in non-legume CC residues leading to N immobilization.

However, mixtures may fail to show increased production, in terms of both above- and below-ground biomass, especially under a low-production environment (Soriano et al., 2023). Some benefits for mixture productivity for below-ground biomass have also been reported

(Sainju et al., 2005). Although there may not be differences in root and/or above-ground biomass production between mixtures and monocultures, the effect of species richness may be reflected in C stock, especially in topsoil layers up to 20 cm and for mineral-associated C fraction (Cordeiro et al., 2022). This highlights the role of rhizodeposition for plant C input, in line with de Notaris et al. (2020), although measurement of root deposition was included in less than 5% of the reviewed studies. As root morphology can have different effects on soil structure, the choice of CC species with specific root traits can have both practical and ecological implications (Hudek et al., 2022). The main benefit of CC species-richness could be contributed by the variability of CC species in their root traits, where mixtures can ameliorate weaknesses of individual CC species, such as lower root biomass production in crimson clover and high root C:N in triticale (Amsili & Kaye, 2021). Amongst root architecture traits, CC species richness especially improved root length and root area, which, in return, increased their positive effects on soil properties, such as SOC content and the composition of soil aggregate-size classes in comparison with monoculture species (Saleem et al., 2020). Similarly, the systems with higher plant diversity also promote higher soil porosity and a greater presence of 30–150 μm pores which are associated with higher microbial enzyme activities due to a higher volume of the soil matrix that can be immediately influenced by microbial decomposition products (Kravchenko et al., 2019). On the other hand, monocultures of some productive species (e.g., hairy vetch and triticale) can be more productive, or equal of that to the best-performing mixtures (Amsili & Kaye, 2021; Saleem et al., 2020) or to that of the spontaneous flora (Fuksa et al., 2013; Sastre et al., 2020). Blanco-Canqui (2022) reported that the SOC storage does not generally differ between CC mixtures and single species and therefore the use of highly productive single species could be a better option than the use of mixtures for SOC accrual, considering that CC higher diversity mixtures can be more costly than single species.

4.3 | CC monoculture vs. mixtures in current research including roots

In spite of the clear benefits of CC mixtures, there are twice as many articles dealing with root traits in monocultures than articles involving mixtures (Figure 4). This probably reflects the relative ease of working with monocultures in terms of crop management and comparing the root traits amongst species. Regarding the species composition in articles on CC mixtures, binary mixtures represent a similar proportion to 3–5 species mixtures,

whereas mixtures with 6 or more species represent only about 20% of all mixtures. Although the contribution of particular species in CC mixture to root traits of the whole mixture is interesting, there is a lack of studies on this aspect as it is relatively more difficult to separate the roots of individual species in a mixture (Saleem et al., 2020). There is also a lack of research on the impact of variable mixture composition on soil traits, especially for high-diversity mixtures (Figure 4).

4.4 | Species contribution in mixtures via their root system

Selected grasses and legumes are generally more productive than non-legume forbs (Soriano et al., 2023) but it is always difficult to make wide generalizations across species within a particular functional group (or plant family). However, it seems that all the main functional groups (*Brassicaceae*, *Fabaceae* and *Poaceae*) offer interesting benefits (Griffiths et al., 2022), so the combination of these three groups probably has the highest potential for fulfilment of a complement of ecosystem services. Most of the available knowledge concerns grasses and legumes. Grasses can increase the between-row root C accumulation in mixtures (Amsili & Kaye, 2021), strongly support root length density (Griffiths et al., 2022), and have a higher potential to increase the labile fraction of SOC as well as total SOC stock in contrast to legumes (Patra et al., 2022; Rosolem et al., 2016). Correspondingly, the highest potential for SOC increase is by grasses in comparison with legumes and legume–grasses mixtures, as reported by Bai et al. (2019). Similarly, Qin et al. (2023) found that non-legume CCs contribute larger SOC accrual than legume CCs due to the larger biomass. However, if based on legumes, a mixture (or legume monoculture) can provide additional N fertilization to the system through biological N_2 fixation with the potential to improve CC above-ground biomass (de Notaris et al., 2020), although this effect was not observed for below-ground biomass with winter vetch (*Vicia villosa*) in the experiment (Mortensen et al., 2021). The frequency of legumes in the mixture is demonstrated in Figure 4 where only about 30% of mixtures were established without legumes. Nitrogen input has a key role in C storage (Wang et al., 2012) as soil organic matter requires more N per unit C than does plant biomass, and consequently the ability of soils to store C is linked to N availability (Cotrufo et al., 2019). The inclusion of legumes in CC mixtures is highly beneficial as it supports high litter quality (lower C:N ratio). This is more effective for the increase of SOC stock in the long term (Frasier et al., 2016; Rosolem et al., 2016) but contrastingly it also increases soil respiration because microorganisms use the easily

degradable C for growth and respiration producing exudates and exopolysaccharides as substrates for microbial communities (Rossi et al., 2020). Nitrogen fixed by the root nodules of legumes also accelerates the SOC storage potential of following crops in the rotation, as a result of the improved microbial activity of the soil microbiome and biomass production by successive crops (Nair et al., 2015), especially in organic systems which are N limited.

According to Amsili and Kaye (2021), the quality of CC residues of various species for subsequent soil transformation should also be considered as increasing both the quantity and the quality and distribution of CC roots may be an effective strategy for building SOC storage. Duval et al. (2016) demonstrated that CCs affected the most dynamic coarse POM fraction directly associated with residue input, and they found that grasses showed higher accumulation than legumes (*Vicia* in their study). The species did not differ in total C accumulation but grasses with high C:N, lignin and cellulose contents promoted accumulation of C in the unprotected coarse POM fraction, whilst root traits of N₂-fixing legumes associated with high labile C input and microbial activity stimulated C accumulation in the protected coarse silt fraction (Rossi et al., 2020). Therefore, the differences in the chemical composition of above-ground biomass should be considered (Duval et al., 2016) when associated with individual species or varieties, the proportion of species in the mixture, as well as biomass water content or leaf–stem ratio.

5 | CC ROOTS DEVELOPMENT UNDER VARIABLE AGRONOMIC MANAGEMENT AND DROUGHT STRESS

5.1 | Pitfall of carefully managed CC experiments

It should be noted that carefully managed and time-consuming field or greenhouse experiments focusing on CC root development and trait measurement may provide valuable supporting results but they are not able to cover the full range of agronomic practices which are highly variable in terms of sowing dates and rates, fertilization, soil tillage or weed regulation. Intensive management, such as ploughing before CC establishment, the absence of weeds or careful weed regulation, special plant arrangement or even irrigation which is widely used in most CC experiments (e.g., Hudek et al., 2022; Kemper et al., 2020; Wendling et al., 2016) can significantly modify root (crop) development and may not always represent real field conditions. For example, ploughing is applied in about 50% of the reviewed studies, whereas no-till is 20%, reduced

tillage is only 10%, and for about 30% of reviewed studies there is no declared information on soil tillage at all (Figure 4). Amongst other agronomic practices, sowing rate or row spacing is not a tested treatment in the CC experiments and recommendations vary across Europe. Although a higher sowing rate (and higher plant density) has the potential for above-ground biomass yield improvement, it also significantly reduces root development, for example, lucerne taproot diameter and lateral root number (Hakl et al., 2021). These above-mentioned conditions may result in overestimates in the results of experiments, similar to the shortcomings in CC experimental methodology as described by Chaplot and Smith (2023). Similarly, some effect on root growth limitation could be expected under reduced soil tillage, together with the reduction of C losses due to lower soil disturbance; for instance, Blanco-Canqui (2022) suggests the tillage system has limited or mixed effect on SOC storage. However, the impact of these practices has not yet been thoroughly investigated in relation to CC root development. Moreover, these agronomic details are often missing in the description of the experiment methodology of the 51 case studies examined in this review, where 65% articles did not provide information about weed regulation (Figure 4). Research of CCs growing together with main crops as under-sown species or various forms of intercropping also needs attention; however, these treatments were also either missing or only briefly mentioned in the case the studies examined.

It can be summarized that we still need precise ‘semi-artificial’ field experiments revealing patterns for root development of particular species in association with SOC storage. However, the challenge here is in making some estimations that are appropriate for practical field conditions, so we also need CC experiments that follow common farmer practices. For future meta-analyses, we need experimental case studies that correctly describe agronomic management practices, at least soil tillage, sowing rate and depth, row spacing (or broadcast sowing), fertilization, weed management and eventually irrigation. This information can help evaluate the contribution of these agronomic operations to CC performance, root development and their potential for SOC stock improvement.

5.2 | CCs fertilization in association with the soil environment

Nutrient supply is also an aspect that requires further attention, especially as the quantity of phyllo- and rhizo-deposition has been shown to be reduced under conditions of higher soil fertility despite significantly higher CC biomass (Mortensen et al., 2021). The N supply especially has a key role, and the results of Bai et al. (2019)

showed the contribution of CC management on SOC storage was more pronounced in conditions with lower N fertiliser input. This is clearly consistent with results showing higher CC root production in an organic farming system compared with conventional systems (Hu et al., 2018). The study of Liang et al. (2022) suggests that root exploitation, and thus plant C inputs into the subsoil, was enhanced in relatively N-poor cropping systems, probably due to a greater need for root exploration to secure sufficient nutrient uptake from the soil (Lynch, 2019). According to Chaplot and Smith (2024), nutrient availability in the soil could be a source of variation in the CC field experiments that accounts for the differences in SOC stock response to CCs. Regarding soil conditions, there could be CC benefits in all kinds of soil but fine-textured soils showed the greatest rates of SOC increase after cover cropping (Jian et al., 2020).

5.3 | Limits for CC adoption and evaluation

Besides agronomic management, there is also a key role linked to weather and climate, as CCs can enhance the SOC stock more in relatively warm environments than in those of cool areas (Bai et al., 2019). The sowing date and the CC growth period together comprise another important factor, as earlier sowing and later date of end of season usually increase CC biomass which in turn leads to larger SOC benefits from CC (Qin et al., 2023). The data suggest that winter CCs are investigated five times more than summer CCs (Figure 3), probably due to an attempt to extend the plant cover over the winter period despite possible problems associated with spring soil cultivation. The length of duration of CC experiments also plays a role when three-year or shorter experiments can be judged too short for changes in SOC stock to be detected and for the temporal dynamics of the changes to be assessed (Chaplot & Smith, 2023).

Indeed, the addition of a significant amount of high-quality CC biomass must be beneficial for SOC storage (Poeplau et al., 2024). There is, however, a practical problem for CC establishment under conditions of insufficient water, which has been found to influence stand establishment with significantly reduced CC growth and performance in rainfed semiarid regions (Brant et al., 2011; Koudahe et al., 2022). Under these conditions, the potential for spontaneous flora (weeds) and volunteers (harvest losses of main crops) for biomass production should be considered compared to the sown CCs. Already cereal harvest losses of around 3% provide around 150 kg ha⁻¹ seeds which can be homogeneously distributed by the harvester. These kinds of unsown vegetation can provide

about 50% of the above-ground biomass energy production (in GJ ha⁻¹) compared with the mean of different CC monocultures in a semiarid environment (Fuksa et al., 2013), and where the reported energy balance between above- and underground biomass followed differences reported for annual crops and grasses (Pausch & Kuzyakov, 2017). Moreover, the SOC storage improvement associated with poorly growing CCs could be questionable where sufficient CC productivity is considered a significant factor contributing to SOC stock improvement (Blanco-Canqui, 2022), especially in cases where additional soil tillage for CC establishment is needed because soil disturbance in relation to CC establishment can increase SOC losses (Rossi et al., 2020). Finally, external carbon costs such as fuel costs for soil preparation and during CC elimination and incorporation were not always considered in some scenario effects (e.g., Poeplau & Don, 2015). Under water-limited conditions, CCs have frequently been found to limit the soil moisture available for the subsequent crop (Koudahe et al., 2022) so there is also a risk for reduction of subsequent crop yields (Fageria et al., 2005). This should also be accounted for in the whole balance between inputs and outputs where spontaneous flora (weeds + volunteers) can also have some potential benefits without additional costs (Fuksa et al., 2013). On the other hand, although weeds and volunteers may have some potential to act as an unsown vegetation cover, productive and well-adapted CC species can significantly increase biomass production over the same growth period in comparison with a fallow (Rosolem et al., 2016) with promising potential for SOC stock improvement (Bai et al., 2019; Cordeiro et al., 2022) and overall soil health improvement (Abdalla et al., 2019; Gollner et al., 2020). These limitations and consequences of CC growth should be definitely considered in the final decision making by farmers where estimation of CC productive potential in a particular year should be balanced with establishment costs as well as with the risk of C emission in association with the additional soil tillage required for CC establishment. Therefore, the CCs should not be recommended in conditions where agronomic or environmental constraints threaten the sufficient productivity of CC stands, and carbon losses may thus be higher than the increase by CC adoption.

6 | CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

The evidence shows that CCs have a clear potential for increasing SOC storage from the growth of their roots throughout various agricultural systems, but this promising benefit cannot be predicted easily across various environments and management. The data suggest that desirable

root morphological traits, such as greater root length, are beneficial for SOC stock as well as for soil structure and soil pore formation and for enabling good penetration of compacted soil. The role of root diameter did not provide a consistent response in SOC storage across studies but fine roots could be considered as effective soil structure formation. Increasing rooting depth was also shown to be a valuable trait, although it is strongly dependent on environment and crop management. Besides root morphology, root chemical composition and quantity, together with the rhizodeposition should be also carefully considered.

CC species differ substantially in their root traits, attendant on their environment, so mixtures can provide a clear benefit from an appropriate combination of root traits supporting soil structure together with C soil stock, although some monocultures could be also effective in a specific environment and mixture contribution to SOC accrual can be marginal. In spite of mixture benefits, the majority of CC root research has been realized on easily managed monocultures, likely for reasons relating to cost and ease of conducting research. Above all, research on CC mixtures needs to be further developed where a selection of species for CC mixtures should be considered, investigations into root traits (not only morphology) and mixture evaluations should also include an assessment of synergy effects in below-ground biomass. Breeding of special CC varieties has also some potential and advanced methods for root evaluations and phenotyping can assist in this aspect, but this is a long-term, highly demanding process with uncertain economic returns for breeders especially where a clear definition of breeding goals is still missing.

Agronomic research to support desirable CC root traits and C root input is needed because of the need to avoid wide generalizations of particular species performance for whole botanical groups or even all CCs. Focus should be given to the efficiency of plant spatial arrangement and low-cost CC establishment methods for optimization of root formation or potential of spontaneous flora, especially in drought-stressed environments. This is of increasing importance because under the influence of climatic change there may be more frequent drought stress effects or a shift in climatic zone. Root formation of CCs and their consequent effect on soil C supply can be significantly modified by agronomic constraints such as reduced soil tillage, higher sowing rate and/or strong weed pressure so CC field studies should provide all necessary agronomic data for possible advanced analyses of the contribution of particular practices.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M. Pisarčík: Conceptualization; formal analysis; writing – original draft; methodology; investigation.

J. Hák: Conceptualization; methodology; project administration; writing – original draft; investigation.
M. Toleikiene: Writing – review and editing.
P. Fuksa: Formal analysis; visualization; investigation.
J. Rasmussen: Conceptualization; writing – review and editing.
R. Hood-Nowotny: Conceptualization; project administration; writing – review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare they have no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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